

EUROqCHARM

EUROpean quality Controlled Harmonization Assuring Reproducible Monitoring and
assessment of plastic pollution

Short report on methods and protocols for the analysis of microplastics in atmospheric samples

EUROqCHARM Short Report

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CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
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About EUROqCHARM

This report is part of a project that has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 Coordination and Support Action programme under Grant Agreement 101003805 (EUROqCHARM).

Plastic pollution has become a global environmental and societal concern in recent years. Numerous protocols have been developed to monitor plastic litter globally, but these are rarely comparable. This has hindered gathering of knowledge regarding pollution sources, development of monitoring programmes and risk assessments, and implementation of mitigation measures. To develop long-term solutions to reduce plastic pollution, it is essential to establish harmonised methodologies. EUROqCHARM will address this by critically reviewing state-of-the-art analytical methods and, taking harmonisation one step further, validating them through an interlaboratory comparison (ILC) study. This will bring together prominent laboratories in environmental plastics analysis and will produce certified reference materials to be marketed for at least three of the four target matrices (water, soil/sediment, biota, air), during and after project completion.

EUROqCHARM recognises that harmonisation for large scale monitoring requires flexibility, comparability and reliability. We will identify Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAP), resulting in a catalogue of RAP procedures for nano-, micro- and macro-plastics for the four target matrices. Each RAP will be validated in terms of Technology Readiness Level (TRL) to decide if further validation is needed (by ILC).

Blueprints for standards, recommendations for policy and legislation and support for the establishment of acceptable reference levels and environmental targets will be given. This will include a roadmap for harmonised data collection and management, where policy analysis and coherence will be integral parts. To maximise impact, EUROqCHARM will also establish and consolidate an operational network for plastic monitoring, stimulating Transnational Joint Actions built on existing and future European and international initiatives.

The multi-stakeholder composition of EUROqCHARM puts the group in a unique position to achieve these ambitious goals.

More information on the project can be found at: www.EUROqCHARM.eu

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Executive Summary

In Task 1.4 from WP1 of the EUROqCHARM project, a Systematic Review was carried out to analyse the matrix- and size- adapted methods reported in the literature for atmospheric samples. Methodological steps from sampling to data management were arranged in Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAPs) and assessed for the Technological Readiness Level (TRL), which may eventually (if not already) be incorporated into plastic monitoring programmes.

Optimising the processes involved in plastic monitoring and analysis is of high priority. Therefore, by introducing RAPs into plastics pollution research, the EUROqCHARM project has been providing guidance for the coordination of monitoring activities at the European level, whilst strengthening the generation of sound scientific knowledge and support strategic actions.

The goal of WP1 T1.4 was achieved through addressing microplastics in the atmosphere matrices. Only a limited number of studies contained descriptions of analytical methods (n=31). The limited number of publications prevent the identification of RAPs, although prototype RAPs were identified. Of the publications that are available, the methods vary across the three subgroups (surface snow, active sampling, total atmospheric fallout). It was not possible to identify any potential RAPs for nanoparticles.

This report is not intended to define the best methods and protocols for analysis, which is the objective of other work packages in EUROqCHARM and dedicated Working Groups, but aims to identify the properties of the fundamental steps of the analytical process and the methods and protocols that are more widely used for monitoring as from scientific literature.

We **showcase the potential of integration of TRLs and RAPs as a tool for systematic description** of analytical procedures for plastics in the environment and as a fundamental decision-making support tool. To support monitoring, it is necessary to define recommended approaches, which are reproducible and comparable when applied between nationals, regions and local. Such methods cannot be recommended if they do not meet the requirements of a certain TRL level.

Acknowledgments

This report was compiled by members of WP1 Task 1.4: Vladimir Nikiforov, Dorte Herzke (NILU), Ralf Kägi (EAWAG), Teresa Moreno (IDAEA/CSIC)

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List of acronyms

Acronyms	Definition
RAPs	Reproducible Analytical Pipelines
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
TRL	Technological Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

Acronym	Full name
NIVA	Norsk institutt for vannforskning <i>Norwegian Institute for Water Research</i>
CNR-ISMAR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – Istituto di Scienze Marine <i>National Research Council, Institute of Marine Sciences (Italy)</i>
CSIC	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas <i>Spanish Research Council</i>
NILU	Norsk institutt for luftforskning <i>Norwegian Institute for Air Research</i>
EAWAG	Eidgenössische Anstalt für Wasserversorgung, Abwasserreinigung und Gewässerschutz <i>Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology</i>

1. Introduction

1.1. Objectives

EUROqCHARM recognises that harmonisation for large-scale monitoring requires flexibility, comparability, and reliability. The main goal of the first EUROqCHARM Work Package (WP1) was to define matrix- and size- adapted methods which may eventually be incorporated into plastic monitoring programmes. To do so, WP1 used a systematic approach to assess methods employed by the international research community and identify state-of-the art procedures for sample collection, sample preparation and analysis of plastics from environmental samples to define matrix- and size- adapted method. **Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAPs)** could be extracted for each element in the analytical chain, resulting in a catalogue of RAP procedures for nano-, micro- and macro-plastics for the four target matrices. Each RAP was further validated in terms of **Technological Readiness Level (TRL)** to decide if further validation is needed.

The workload was thereby divided across four tasks addressing plastics in different size ranges (nano-, micro-, macroplastics) in different matrices (water, soil/sediment, air, biota). The specific objectives of WP1 were to:

- Identify existing methods - including the level of currently applied QA/QC procedures for the quantification of nano-, micro-, and macro-plastics in different matrices.
- Evaluate the identified methods for their suitability to be incorporated into monitoring programmes including their advantages and limitations. The most promising methods were suggested for validation and quality control in WP2 or direct implementation into WP3.

Therefore, the **key outputs** of WP1 were to compile existing methods and protocols used to quantify plastics in environmental matrices (using RAPs), evaluate them for further validation (WP2) or direct implementation in monitoring programmes (WP3);

The main actions in WP1 were:

- Systematic literature review;
- Synthesis of existing methods and procedures;
- Compilation of Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAPs);
- Analyses of methods Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT);
- Suggestions for critical revisions of identified monitoring methods.

All these objectives and tasks were attempted for plastic of sizes ranging from macro- to nanoplastics in water, sediment, biota and air, with both marine and terrestrial environments.

In the present report, **the outputs from microplastics in atmosphere are presented.**

2. Methods

The difference between this Task (T1.4) and other tasks of WP1 (plastic in water, in biota, in soil/sediment) is that a much smaller number of papers were available for review. Therefore, the papers on microplastics in air were necessarily analysed using a traditional review approach. The aim remained to identify repeatable patterns in sampling and analysis, which could be indications of future potential Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAPs). All data were collected by the task leader (NILU) and a general quality control/quality assurance performed. Further details on the method can be found in Aliani et al. (2023).

3. Results

Seventy-seven papers related to plastic in the air were identified through the literature review process, only 31 of which included descriptions of analytical methods. Only the papers describing analysis of environmental samples were retained. For example, papers related to fibre emissions from washing/drying machines, or ventilation systems were excluded. Methods were considered for review if the sampling procedure was included in two or more papers. This further reduced the number of relevant papers to 13, which could be subsequently divided into three subgroups as a basis for potential RAPs depending on sample collection (Table 1).

The diagrams related to microplastic in air have been made in shades of grey to emphasize the lack of RAPs but their potential as prototypes (e.g., Figure 1). There was no indication on potential RAPs for nanoparticles.

Different shaped particles ranging in size from 5 mm to 5 µm have been reported in environmental air samples, including fibres, fragments, and foams. Several types of polymers have been identified, although most effort has been on reporting the concentrations of microplastics in air as per volume, per area or deposition rate per area.

Table 1. The number of inspected and reviewed papers on particular sampling type for air

Step	Number of papers
Number of papers selected for review by keywords	77
Method papers remaining under review after detailed inspection	31
Subgroup 1: Methods for microplastic in surface snow by µFTIR	3
Subgroup 2: Methods for microplastic by active sampling (filtration) of air	5
Subgroup 3: Methods for microplastic in total atmospheric fallout (dry & wet deposition)	5

Figure 1 – Analytical pipeline for microplastics in the air, based on sample collection and reporting.

3.1. Methods for microplastic analysis in surface snow

The three publications present methods for the analysis of microplastics in surface snow. These are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Methods for analysis of microplastics in surface snow samples using μ FTIR.

Ref No.	Layer depth, cm	Volume sampled, L	Processed Volume, mL	Instrumental method	LOD, μ m	Analysis filter
Bergmann et al. 2019	"thin, surface"	n.a.	varied	μ FTIR	11	Anodisc 0.2 μ m/25 mm
Parolini et al. 2021	n.a.	2	whole, ca 500	μ FTIR	10	Cellulose 1 μ m/47 mm
Pastorino et al. 2021	10-15	0.75	whole	μ FTIR	10	Paper 6 μ m/n.a.

The methods focused on the collection of a fresh snow layer, melting, filtering and analysis by μ FTIR. In short, these methods consisted of the following steps:

1. Fresh snow samples were collected with metal tool into glass or metal container. There was no specification on the optimal or representative volume required.
2. Samples were transported to the laboratory. Yet, preserving the frozen state was not considered critical.
3. Samples were allowed to melt.
4. Samples were filtered. All three publications used different filter papers.
5. The volume of sample processed is dependent on the possibility of particles to clog the filters. It may be necessary to filter in replicates to avoid clogging.
6. Procedural controls including blanks and lab air controls are important all different measures were implemented across the three papers. It is not yet possible to generalized this. Notably, all groups approached the sampling location from downwind.
7. Plastic quantification was performed using μ FTIR.
8. The size limit of detection (LOD) was ca. 10 μ m, however the LOD for number of particles has not been evaluated.
9. Data was reported as number of microplastic particles per m².
10. The full μ FTIR image remains on file for retrospective analysis in the future in a harmonized way, if necessary.

The potential RAP is presented in Figure 2. It is plausible that in the future a RAP will be based on the described procedure.

Figure 2 – RAP prototype for monitoring by analysis of fresh snow.

3.2. Methods for microplastic analysis using active sampling (filtration) of air

Five papers contained a description of methods using active sampling for microplastics (Table 3).

Table 3. Methods for microplastic analysis by active sampling (filtration) of air (reporting - number/m³)

Ref no.	rate, L/min	Volume, m ³	pores, μm	diameter, mm	material	organics removal	Instrumental method
Allen et al. 2020	50	18	n.a	47	Quartz	yes	μRaman
Li et al. 2020	5	2	0.8	47	Mixed cellulose ester	no	SEM-EDX
Pedrotti et al. 2021	ca 50	100-400	0.45	47	Cellulose acetate	no	stereomicroscope
Peller et al. 2019	3	ca 100	0.2	25	PTFE	no	microscope
Prata et al. 2020	5	44	n.a	n.a	Quartz	yes	stereomicroscope

All five papers used different approaches in their analysis such that:

1. Sampling rate ranged from 3 to 50 L/min.
2. Sampling volume ranged from 2 to 400 m³.
3. Filters used: two times Quartz, two times cellulose ester, once PTFE.
4. Pore sized ranged from 0.2-0.8 μm, diameter mainly 47 mm, with 25 mm used once.
5. Two methods applied organic removal whereas three did not perform this step.
6. Two methods used a stereomicroscope, the remaining three methods used μRaman, SEM-EDX, and a microscope separately.

The differences between methods are shown on Figure 3. No indication to potential future RAP can be concluded from the current state of the analyses by active sampling.

Figure 3 – Lack of unified analytical pipeline for analysis of microplastics in air based on active sampling.

3.3. Methods for microplastic in total atmospheric fallout (dry & wet deposition)

Five papers described methods for analysis of microplastic in integrated samples of wet and dry deposition (Table 4).

Table 4. Methods for microplastic by active sampling (filtration) of air (collection of total atmospheric fallout (dry & wet deposition, reporting - number/m³ m²/day)

Paper no.	sampling time, day	Collector D, mm	Collector	Filter pore, μm	Filter material	Method 1	Method 2	LOD, mm
Dris et al. 2015	7-30	570	20L glass	1.6	Glass fibre	Stereo microscope	none	100
Dris et al. 2016	n.a.	570	20L glass	1.6	Glass fibre	Stereo microscope	none	50
Cai et al. 2017	30-31	150	5.3L glass	1	Glass fibre	Stereo microscope	μFTIR	20-100
Knobloch et al. 2021	6	133/220	2-4L glass	1.2	Glass fibre	Stereo microscope	μFTIR	20
Szewc et al. 2021	1-8	650	20L glass	1.6	Glass fibre	Stereo microscope	μFTIR	5

All the five papers describe very similar procedure. The three more recent papers were based on the two earlier ones (Dris et al. 2015, 2016).

1. Sampling time and collector orifice vary, depending on the purpose.
2. All containers were made of glass (bottles or beaker), as well as the filters.
3. Filter diameter was 1-1.6 μm : well below size-based LOD but wide enough to ease filtering.
4. Stereomicroscope was the main acquisition method with μFTIR added later for identification of polymer type.
5. Minimal detected size gradually improved over 6 years from 100 to 5 μm .
6. All information can be preserved for retrospective processing by harmonised methods.

The outline of potential RAP for monitoring microplastic in air by analysis of wet and dry deposition by stereomicroscopy and μFTIR is presented in Figure 4. It is plausible that RAP in the future will be based on the described procedure.

Figure 4 – RAP prototype for monitoring microplastic in air by analysis of wet and dry deposition by stereomicroscopy and μFTIR .

3.4. TRLs for monitoring plastics in air

Table 5. Summary table of TRLs for microplastic analysis in air samples

TRL	Survey design	Sample collection	Sample preparation	Analytical detection	Plastic quantification	QA/QC	Data reporting
1							
2	Concept application and formulation	Concept application and formulation – active sampling	Concept application and formulation – filtration - active sampling, snow sampling	Concept application and formulation – SEM-EDX, Microscope, Raman - active sampling	Concept application and formulation – items/ m^3 - active sampling	Concept application and formulation	
3		Feasibility – snow sampling, wet and dry deposition					feasibility
4				μRaman			
5				μFTIR , Stereomicroscope			
6			Demonstration in relevant environment – filtration - total fallout	Demonstration in relevant environment – μFTIR – total fallout, snow sampling	Demonstration in relevant environment – items/ m^2 ; items/ m^2/day - snow sampling, total fallout		
7							
8							
9							

4. Discussion

Only a limited number of studies are available on the sampling of microplastics in air. Of the publications that are available, the methods vary across the three subgroups (surface snow, active sampling, total atmospheric fallout). μ FTIR and stereomicroscope appeared to be the main analytical identification and quantification methods, respectively. Total atmospheric fallout collected over period of 1-30 days was used for integrated assessment and fresh surface snow – for time-resolved events. Three publications describe use of mass-spectrometry for identification and quantification of plastics in air as mass per volume, but no monitoring-ready methods have been described yet. Active air sampling is in its initial stages of testing/development and not ready for implementation in monitoring yet.

The main outcome of our survey is that there are not enough publications to support a SR as the presence of plastic in air is a new addition to the problem of environmental plastics. Only recently, some papers have presented the problem and the science behind is still too young to organise a full monitoring plan based upon shared methods.

There are many methods used so far to sample air plastics, but discussion is welcome in the scientific community on the protocols that better fit the monitoring needs at large scale. Promising results can be foreseen but this science has still too many knowledge gaps.

5. Conclusion

The major conclusions deduced from the review were:

1. The number of publications with adequately described method is too small for statistical analysis (13 papers).
2. The three main approaches are based on active sampling, collection of the total atmospheric fallout and analysis of plastic in snow to approach plastic in air.
3. All adequately described methods reported a number of particles (per m^3 , per m^2 , or per m^2/h), not a mass fraction of plastic.
4. Air is a relatively clean matrix, therefore no major difficulties can be expected in direct implementation of RAPs for other matrixes to air analysis.
5. Representative and reproducible sampling is appeared to be the least developed analytical step.
6. Sampling in air is not technologically ready to be included in large scale monitoring programs.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

1. Prioritize method development for plastic in air.
2. Focus on sampling representativity and reproducibility.
3. Pay attention to measurement of mass-fraction of plastic, not only number of particles.
4. More research is needed on air sampling procedures to exploit PM10 monitoring network

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